

CASE STUDY ON MANAGEMENT RISK MANAGEMENT IN A PUBLIC HOSPITAL IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

Purpose: *This paper contains considerations regarding the case study, aims to identify managerial risks in the health system.*

Methodology: *In this study, modern research techniques were used, such as: the bibliographic study method and the interview method.*

Findings: *It can be appreciated that the health unit carries out its activity based on the legislation in force which has proved to be very cumbersome and sometimes unclear.*

Research limitations / implications: *This research is performed in a public hospital in Romania.*

Practical implications: *The identification of managerial risks, other than clinical ones, contributes to the efficiency of the system, the improvement of patient safety and the elimination of managerial mistakes.*

Originality: *This paper is based on interviews with employees of the health unit, the originality of the opinions is the important element that contributed to this research.*

Keywords: *risk, management, health*

Introduction

Like any enterprise, institution, company, and health units in Romania, they carry out their activity so that the risks are permanently present. For this reason, the management of health units must pay special attention to risks, and this requires a careful, insistent and in-depth analysis of all the risks and their effects.

Analyzing the health system, it can be stated that it can be evaluated as one of the largest "enterprises" in which activities are diversified.

Underlying good risk management are the general principles that, applied according to standards, can make a beneficial contribution to healthcare facilities.

These principles act as a guide, orientation, channeling and protection of values, so that the objectives are achieved. For this, the following must be kept in mind: the concern for creating, protecting and improving performance and value; risk management to be an integral part of processes and decision-making, being considered an act of responsibility of the manager; transparency of risk management, etc.

Risk management in healthcare units in Romania is characterized as a complex process, which cannot be treated as a simple review, and no matter how the problem is posed, the systemic approach to risk management will remain essential.

The regulatory activity in the field of health, represents a way in which the principles underlying public health are implemented.

The regulations regarding the risk management in hospitals are the norms elaborated and endorsed by the Ministry of Health and which represent reference documents.

Organizational culture is also an important factor that makes its mark in the management of managerial risks, so it is considered a priority for managers. Organizational culture is the sum of all the values in the health unit, and which represents the "lifestyle" of the health unit. Employees, through the exercise of the profession, achieve their goals, objectives that underlie professional values.

Risk management in healthcare units focuses on the risks that can affect both patients and employees and the medical institution.

Effective risk management is based primarily on knowledge of risks and at the same time the focus is on eliminating unacceptable risks.

Considerations regarding the risk management in the specialized literature

In order to paint an overall picture of what management is, we can call on the opinions of great specialists in the field, who are "school creators" and who through their countless publications and stories have highlighted the role and essence of leadership. What they offer us is in fact the evolution of management, of everything that the art of leadership means.

The father of scientific management, Frederick Taylor (USA), is constantly attracted and concerned about the evolution of management as a science. The best results are obtained due to the conception and management style approached by each institution, its own conception which is based on theoretical notions and which can be applied not only in industry but also in the healthcare system. Having at hand the theoretical scientific bases, together with everything that represents elements belonging to the decision-making field, changes and changes in health, is the health reform, all having an essential contribution to obtaining an efficient and effective management that is appreciated in health.

An essential support of this research is based on the literature, publications and evaluations - health system research. Decentralization in Romania is one of the concerns of political factors and is mainly aimed at public administration, characteristic of the unitary system. In this sense, we can say that the health field is anchored on a multitude of regulations and legal norms based on the Fundamental Law of the country - the Romanian Constitution.

Theoretical and practical reasons have made the health system reform focus not only on the factors that are responsible for health care, but also on the management and coordination functions, aimed at the management of the public health system.

The management of the public health system has also undergone some changes due to the transformations that have occurred over time, more precisely it has adapted to current needs. The transition from one system to another and their improvement has only added value in terms of patient health as well as the sphere of coordination and in all that management means.

Basically, the management developed with the health reform, a reform that was constantly subject to legislative changes and often could not bend to the real situation, thus, the application of the rules presenting a discomfort for those involved. Following a research, it was shown that in the Romanian public health system, decision makers, respectively hospital managers, did not manage the situation sufficiently and conscientiously, thus, some areas managed improperly were discovered. Transparency regarding the allocation of resources, as well as their sometimes unjustified allocation criteria have led to the deterioration of the system.

Even the World Health Organization expresses its point of view, stating that health has an important role, rising to the rank of law, representing a "national treasure", which has the power to support the evolution of a society. It should be emphasized that the activity of the health system more precisely, the Romanian management system is somewhat influenced by the level of European and even global

management, which is a benefit for Romania. This benefit can be materialized in the transfer of knowledge, methods, techniques, which for us is a progress.

Scientist Peter Drucker drew attention through his publications that society is forced to accept modern management, and those who do not adapt will have unpleasant surprises. This entails a change, which can only be done with efficient management.

Management some time ago focused largely on speed and speed, and less on the target - target, and this attracted imbalances. Modern management must look for talent among the employees that managers have, in order to exponentially increase efficiency, value and quality, at the same time it must stimulate thinking with their own mechanisms to accelerate innovation.

Foreign authors, such as English or French, had a major influence on Romanian theorists, concerned with the evolution of management. An American study shows us that globalization in the medical field, presents differences regarding the problems of health systems, and collaboration and international relations are not in the field of news. (Norbert Stenczel)

If we refer in a global context, the problems multiply, which determines the detailed examination of some aspects related to the distribution of the labor force, the composition, the migration of the medical staff, as well as its size. The study of the factors related to the culture of each country, geography and economic development should not be neglected.

Another aspect of public health in a global context is economic development and the resources of each country. All attention is focused on gross domestic product (GDP), which is a "decision" factor in terms of population health. The higher the GDP, the higher the investment in health, the higher the labor force, which leads to better health management. Romania is not among the leading places in the European Union in terms of funding, on the contrary it is half the EU average, more precisely, it is close to 5% of GDP (State of Health in the EU, 2009)

In the healthcare system, financial management is one of the important links that has the role of developing the medical field, presenting at the same time a bridge of communication between the specialists in the field and top manager. In the field of health, the increase in the needs of society leads to an increase in financial resources and which is manifesting itself in an accelerated manner.

When it comes to studying global health systems, it is necessary and appropriate to analyze the impact that the field of human resources can have on health reform. The trends of globalization in health are represented by achieving the goals that lead to efficiency, quality and equity.

The socio-demographic factor represents a key role, which directs our attention to the aging population and which differs from one country to another. The aging of the population requires the health system to supplement the workforce in the medical field. Another aspect is the replacement of the elderly medical staff with a young medical staff, eager to embrace the medical career.

In modern management, in addition to the fields directly related to medical activity, an important field is also technical and technological, and here we refer to the use of information and communication technology, and the role it plays in the decision-making process.

Human resource management (HR) should, in practice, not be different from other areas, as they are the main source that proves to be inexhaustible and can be adapted to current needs. The complexity of the relationship between human resources and health requires a thorough and in-depth study.

As the public health field is also a publicly funded system, human resource costs are high and certainly affect the employment of efficient specialists, for which a workforce balance must be found.

Characteristic of all developing countries, is the migration of health personnel from rural to urban areas, directing professionals to developed countries, this labor mobility, without human resource planning, lead to an imbalance difficult to control.

Case study on managerial risk management in a public hospital in Romania

The hospital being characterized as a complex system, it represents the support of health care of the population, and which by its nature and configuration is made up of subsystems that interrelate with each other (departments, laboratories, etc.). For these reasons, the hospital as a public entity must focus on the quality of medical services, proactive management, performance and flexibility. The hospital being a complex system, it can be stated that it is a socio-technical system, in which the individual, as a human being is considered a component of this system. Technically speaking, we can say that the hospital has the appearance of a company that provides services in favor of customers. We can practically associate this hospital environment with a business environment, in which the risks can influence it so that it can lead to insecurity. That is why a rigorous, efficient management, which is concerned with maintaining standards, looking for new methods that support evolution, inevitably leads to competitiveness and performance. At present, risk management is no longer perceived as a compliance issue, but is considered as an integral part of the decision-making process.

The course of history has shown us that hospitals in Romania are constantly facing an increasing increase in demand for medical services, which entails an increase in costs and risks. From a theoretical point of view, efficiency and quality should not be missing from the medical act, but in practice it turns out that these two factors are not always present.

The real image of a public hospital in Romania is drawn after a careful analysis that at the same time shows us the evolution of the reform process.

This presentation is made in a public hospital in Romania, which is part of the research activity aimed at managerial risks.

Thus, the health unit carries out its activity based on legal norms and regulations, joining the system and operational procedures regarding risk management. Being one of the studied departments, that of quality management, we can say that it represents an important link in the management process of the health unit, and that the analysis shows that this department faces various problems that affect to some extent the activities of both departments. as well as the hospital. The most acute problems are not only related to the specialized personnel within this sector, but also to problems related to the perception of the sanitary personnel at the level of sections, keeping in mind the following:

- Difficulties in organizing the compartment: Surprisingly, one of the problems comes from the direction of ANMCS, which turns out that it has not issued an order on the specific duties of each employee in the department responsible for quality management, and this is stipulated only at plan level, following that on future to materialize.
- Another problem reported is the lack of a head of service to coordinate and train the staff of the department, and this makes the activity of employees have a chaotic course. The existence of the vacancy vacated six months ago does not seem to be on the management's priority list.
- Insufficient staffing is a general problem at the hospital level.
- Section level issues: A less pleasant situation is the disinterest of the staff in the departments and compartments of the hospital regarding the risk management, practically, they do not want to assume the risks, and the obligations are passed on to other colleagues. The receptivity and interest of the medical staff is very low, they use materials from the Google application, which has no connection and does not meet the needs of the health unit.

The quality management department and its attributions are misperceived by the medical staff, who expect that all the specific activity of the management will be performed only by the persons specialized in this field without involving the medical staff from the departments and compartments.

The presence of the risk of non-fulfillment of the service activities, due to the resistance of the medical staff and the refusal to implement the requirements, is another impediment in performing the service tasks of the department.

In the absence of sufficient involvement, often total disinterest, in this context and the responsibilities were misunderstood, moreover, this compartment is considered useless.

Regarding the field of danger, namely labor protection and PSI, an important aspect is that the perception of employees is good, and they are beginning to realize that the rules are common sense and come to their aid, however we still encounter areas in that disinterest and implementation of the instructions are present. Another problem facing the sub-fund is the inadequacy of funds and action instruments. The most burning issue is related to legislation, legislation that has gaps, difficult to understand, what is to be done is not stated correctly, and for this reason there is confusion. National legislation is linked to European norms, but the mismatch of work systems is obvious. Another aspect regarding the legislation is the standardization, namely, the legislation does not specify the number of employees for this sector, for this reason this compartment is insufficiently standardized which leads to the difficult development of activities.

Human Resources (HR), one of the most important areas, falls in the same directions as the other departments. It is noted that there are trends in adapting to European legislation, but European standards have not been reached, so the legislation needs to be improved and updated.

One of the weaknesses of this field is the insufficient staff and the lack of sufficient involvement in carrying out the service activities. The staff inside the compartment consider that they carry out their activity in a demanding atmosphere due to the large volume of activities, legislative changes, a burning issue is related to the deadlines that must be met regardless of conditions (number of staff and overtime). In the opinion of some employees, in the activity of human resources, there is a need for a much more active participation in professional training courses, and especially for a change of mentality. The staff outside the compartment within the health unit do not appreciate and are not aware of the work done by the employees of the R.U.N.O.S.

Although the financial-accounting department works relatively well, the collaboration of the financial department with the hospital management is very good, there are still situations in which the activity is hampered by certain external factors. Despite the fact that, from a theoretical point of view, the health unit is located at the level of European Union standards, practically the situation is not in accordance with the theory. The factors that contribute to the difficulty of meeting the standards are related to the insufficient financial support from the state, the political nuances, but also to the need to improve the staff at the level of requirements.

Conclusions

Although the health system is considered a priority, political factors have contributed through its levers so that this system has not benefited from unitary management.

It can be appreciated that the health unit carries out its activity based on the legislation in force, legislation that has proven to be very cumbersome, with gaps, often unclear. Another aspect is that European legislation does not always comply with our health system, which leads to a functional imbalance.

In other words, the legislative deficiencies, together with the organizational problems both at managerial and compartmental level, the lack of involvement, as well as the lack of an organizational culture lead to the difficulty of the health unit's activity.

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